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River Current Energy Devices: Progress and Challenges for Power System Modeling

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Abstract

River energy devices are poised to provide significant energy to electrical grids and in particular to river-based communities in Alaska. To facilitate large-scale adoption of river energy devices, a standard suite of power system models is necessary to perform interconnection or stability studies whether the device be connected to an isolated microgrid, a distribution system, or large transmission system. This work reviews the power system modeling that has been performed for river energy devices and similar devices, including device testing and data collection from the Tanana River Test Site in Nenana, Alaska. Additionally, it is proposed to leverage power system models used for wind generators, and augment the relevant IEEE standards for inverter-based resources and distributed energy resources for use for power system modeling of river energy devices. We propose that the `regc_a`, `reec_a`, and `repc_a` models be used to represent river energy devices and that hydro-turbine power system models need to be developed or the need for them evaluated. A subset of the IEEE 1547 and 2800 standard tests are also proposed to assist with the parameterization and development of the proposed river energy devices models.

Keywords: River Energy Devices; Current Energy Converters; Marine Hydro Kinetic Devices; Power System Modeling

1. Introduction

Energy from rivers can be captured in the form of water current energy. Across the United States there is 99 TWh/yr of river energy available [1]. The majority of this energy potential resides in the Mississippi River and within the state of Alaska at 21 TWh/yr for Alaska [2].

In particular, remote Alaskan communities are uniquely positioned to benefit from river energy devices [3]. Alaska has over 200 remote islanded microgrids [4] of which over 50 communities are along the Yukon and Kuskokwim watershed rivers in Alaska. These microgrids are primarily powered by diesel generators, whose fuel is barged or flown to communities at prices that in some communities exceeded \$16/gallon in 2022 [5]. In part due to this high cost of fuel and consequentially high cost of electricity, remote Alaskan communities have been at the forefront of integrating renewable energy such as wind and solar. Most notably for river energy, the community of Iguigig, Alaska has been in partnership with Ocean Renewable Power Company (ORPC), the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), and Deerstone Consulting to test multiple deployments of ORPC's RivGen device, with the RivGen 2.1 and a battery energy storage system installed in 2022 [6].

Numerous challenges exist for river energy devices to be as commercially ready as wind turbines are today. Environmental challenges include surface debris, interactions with fish and marine species, river freezing, and frazil

ice in cold climate environments such as Alaska during river freeze-up [7]. River energy faces similar, though more minimal, resource variability challenges as wind energy. Tidal energy resources are estimated to have an order of magnitude less variability than wind energy resources [8], and river energy resources have less variability than tidal resources. River energy devices have been designed with similar components to wind generators [9], and therefore also face similar grid integration challenges and bring similar opportunities.

To date, river energy assessments, device modeling, and analysis has primarily focused on site assessments, turbine efficiency improvement, and environmental impacts [9]. These existing studies have focused on the water and mechanical components of river energy devices. The electrical data that has been collected from in-river testing was collected for the purpose of generating power curves, per IEC standard 62600-300 [10].

Few studies have addressed electrical and power system integration components of river energy devices. In addition, power system integration or interconnection studies or grid expansion studies require electrical models developed for industry standard power system simulation tools such as Siemens PTI PSSe, General Electric PSLF, and DiGSILENT PowerFactory. As river energy device technology matures to the point of needing grid interconnection studies, standard power system models will need to be developed. Due to the similarities between river and wind energy devices, there is the opportunity for technological leap-frogging of river energy device power system modeling using the current standard wind generator power system models. This can be achieved through testing and validation and also of river energy device grid services capability requirements through IEEE standards [11,12].

This work reviews the studies that have performed electrical and power system tests and simulations of river energy devices. Updates are provided on river energy device in-river tests and electrical data collected from the Tanana River Test Site in Nenana, Alaska, highlighting the need for new types of tests to aid power system model development. In addition, proposed next steps will be outlined for new testing of river energy devices, models for power system modeling, and standards for grid services capabilities. The contribution of this work is to provide review of the current status of river energy devices and propose steps to bring the technology closer to large-scale grid integration.

2. Testing and Data

River current energy device testing in Alaska started in 2008 in Ruby, Alaska. Since then device testing has occurred throughout the state including at the Tanana River Test Site. The Tanana River Test Site (TRTS) in Nenana, Alaska has been testing river energy devices since 2012. The list of devices that have been tested in Alaska, including at TRTS is outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. River Energy Devices tested in Alaska [6,7,13-15]

Company	Device	Turbine Type	Power Capacity (kW)	Year	Location
New Energy	EnCurrent	VA	5	2008, 2009, 2010	Ruby
New Energy	EnCurrent	VA	25	2010	Eagle
ORPC	RivGen TM	CF	40	2019, 2021	Igiugig
Oceana Energy Company	Oceana River Energy Converter	HA	25	2014,2015	TRTS
Renerge, Inc.	Waterhorse	OF	7	2020, 2021	TRTS
BladeRunner Energy, Inc.	BladeRunner	HA	5	2021, 2022, 2023	TRTS
New Energy	EnviroGen	VA	5	2016-2018, 2021, 2023	TRTS

The device tests and data collected from the TRTS have primarily been aimed to determine turbine efficiencies using the available power in the swept area of the turbine compared to the measured DC power output, and the power curves within the range of river velocities during testing [16, 17].

3. Steady State and Dynamic Power System Modeling

Formative work on modeling and simulation of river and tidal generators was performed in [18], which outlined the fundamental components of these devices and characterized the performance of an ORPC RivGenTM. These

fundamental components, also outlined in [9], include a turbine, generator, passive or active rectifier, voltage source inverter, and potentially capacitors or battery banks for smoothing or power conditioning.

However, limited studies have performed power system simulations specifically of current energy converters (CEC), whether for tidal or river resources. Most of these studies have focused on steady state characterization or dynamic response characterization of the devices or their control systems or validation of device models using steady state or time domain dynamic power system simulations.

4. Applicability of Wind Generation Standard Power System Models and Interconnection Standards for River Energy Devices

Standard power system models for wind generators were developed by WECC and have gone through numerous iterations over two decades [19, 20]. The current standard suite of power system models for type 3 and 4 wind generators include: regc_a, reec_a, reec_b, wtgt_a, wtgar_a, wtgpt_a, wtgtrq_a, and repc_a [20].

The directly relevant models for river energy devices are the regc_a, reec_a, and repc_a. These or similar versions of these models are used for inverter-based resources (IBRs) in general, which is why they are applicable to river energy devices which have the power electronic interface to the grid. These models are often used without any additional models, and capable of simulating the dynamics of IBRs on their own.

The other wind-specific models capture dynamics related to specific wind turbine dynamics that would need to be re-evaluated for their usefulness and parameterized to represent hydro dynamics in a river setting. It is possible that fundamentally different models, beyond new parameter settings, may be warranted to capture the hydro turbine dynamics. However, in order to evaluate these models, test data needs to be collected that can be used to develop and validate the entirely new models. This will also be necessary for the subset of non-turbine based river CECs.

5. Proposed Next Steps for Power System Model Development for River Energy Devices

Testing of river energy devices is needed which is designed to create data to develop and validate power system models. The current testing and collected electrical data is designed to create data to develop power curves and evaluate device efficiencies. Dynamic power system models simulate the response of a device to disturbances to verify that both the device is internally stable and will not create instabilities in the system it is being connected to. IBRs are now required to provide grid services through their power electronic controls to assist with maintaining the stability of the system.

Large-scale IBRs (typically considered greater than 5 MW) need to adhere to IEEE Standard 2800 [11]. The controls, capabilities, and protection that this standard specifies for grid-connected IBRs includes reactive power, active power, voltage, frequency, rate-of-change-of-frequency (ROCOF), voltage phase angle change ride-through, and power quality [11]. Small-scale IBRs which are connected at the distribution level, called distributed energy resources (DERs), are required to a similar standard, IEEE Standard 1547 [12]. This standard requirements includes those items listed for IEEE Standard 2800 and grounding, disconnects, communications interoperability, and islanding [12].

Both standards outline the need for IBRs and DERs to aid or at least not disrupt system stability by a similar set of capabilities and controls. In addition, a suite of conforming tests are listed in both standards. These standards and suite of tests are relevant and applicable to river energy devices when interconnecting with either large transmission systems, distribution systems, or isolated microgrids such as those found in Alaska.

At this time, few devices have reached the stage of interconnection with grids and there are no standard models to assess the standards IEEE 1547 or 2800. Testing following IEEE 1547 or 2800 procedures will be the most common protocol. Therefore, two categories of testing are needed to move the technology closer to large-scale adoption: 1) tests to develop hydro-turbine power system models and validate regc_a, reec_a, and repc_a models, and then 2) the IEEE 1547 or 2800 tests.

At this stage of development useful device tests to develop hydro-turbine power system models and validate regc_a, reec_a, and repc_a modes include river current changes, load changes, voltage changes, frequency changes, and fault responses. These tests will capture the response of these devices to standard changes of the turbine and the grid to help define the power system models. In addition, these tests will need to have fast data acquisition capabilities to capture electro-mechanical dynamics (milliseconds) and electro-magnetic transients (microseconds). Some of these tests are feasible to perform during in-river testing of devices, such as river current changes, load changes, and voltage changes.

Other tests will need to be performed by implementing hardware-in-the-loop tests with a grid emulator and fault emulator, such as frequency changes and fault responses.

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